

From a *Barrio Chino* urban stigma to the Raval cultural brand: urban memory and cultural policies in the renewal of central Barcelona

Joaquim Rius-Ulldemolins

University of Valencia

Joaquim.rius@uv.es

Ricardo Klein

University of Valencia

Ricardo.Klein@uv.es

Department of Sociology and Social Anthropology

Faculty of Social Sciences

Avinguda Tarongers, 4b

46008 València

Spain

Correspondence author

Joaquim Rius-Ulldemolins

University of Valencia

Joaquim.rius@uv.es

Abstract

Barcelona, and especially, its historic centre has undergone a profound transformation from an industrial city to a global tourism and services centre. Some authors insist on the destructive nature of the urban regeneration of the historic Barcelona district of Raval as a process of de-identification of the city centre or as an intentional falsification of its identity to turn it into a tourist space. However, as we discuss in this paper, urban branding and urban change projects should address not only the infrastructural issues of transformation, but also the development of new urban branding based on recreating a memory of the place. Thus, in the case of Raval, the urban and cultural planning led by the local government and the development of cultural institutions took place as part of the construction and revitalisation of the identity of the neighbourhood from that of a *barrio chino* red-light district stigma to one of a new cultural quarter.

Keywords: urban regeneration, cultural policy, urban branding, artistic world, Raval, Barcelona

Introduction

Interventions in the historic and central districts of European cities by installing large cultural infrastructures have been an upward urban planning trend since the 1970s [1,2]. Perhaps the most emblematic operation in Europe from this period is the Georges Pompidou Centre in France because of the effect it had on the adjacent neighbourhoods of Les Halles and Le Marais and its conversion into a space for nightlife and cultural consumption [3,4]. Thus, the implementation of this large-scale urban policy which operated through culture was accused of altering the historical urban layout of the area and in so doing, manoeuvring social change and rupturing and denying the city's popular history [5]. Since then, there has been a lot of academic debate in the field of urban planning about the impact of the operations involved in constructing large cultural infrastructures, the associated implications in terms of urban change, and their more sustainable and participatory alternatives [6,7].

Likewise, these projects often face active opposition by neighbourhood residents or cultural heritage defence sectors denouncing the destruction of the urban heritage (i.e., the urban layout or buildings), social fabric, or historical memory of areas [8,9]. In some cases, these projects have been accused of trying to deliberately eliminate the memory of spaces or falsifying their urban histories [9,10]. However, while in the 19th and early 20th centuries this purpose did exist, this logic had changed by the end of the 20th century. To a certain extent, symbolic elements are no longer secondary or seen as obstacles to change in new urban planning policies. Rather, the relationship has reversed, with the revitalisation of memory becoming one of the main positive consequences of urban regeneration processes [11,12]. Thus, the new place-making paradigm from the urban cultural policies developed in the 1990s made the artistic community an ally in the process of using the symbolic elements of places as a means for their social and spatial transformation [13,14].

The symbolic dimensions of urban change have been poorly studied to date. This is especially true if we consider that many of the neighbourhoods subjected to urban regeneration are historical spaces which are, therefore, both symbolically loaded and degraded by the stigmas they may carry (such as being dangerous areas or red-light districts). The active role of cultural policies and institutions in the redefinition and historical recovery of the memory of the urban districts in which they are located has been little studied thus far. In this sense, it seems appropriate to highlight the relationship of certain urban transformation paths, such as in the example of the Raval in central Barcelona, as a complex and paradoxical example in which the memory of the place was activated precisely during its own regeneration process. In addition, in this example, urban planning was not the only factor that reflected cultural policies, rather, the memory policies of cultural institutions such as the Centre for Contemporary Culture of Barcelona (CCCB) played an especially prominent role in fostering the singularities of this urban space and its historical journey [15]. Other articles have analysed how Barcelona is the unexpected result both of different planning initiatives and historical processes, some of which are conflicting [16,17].

Thus, there were three interacting dimensions in the case of Raval: the scope of the planning, the diverse population living in the neighbourhood and its cultural expression, and the symbolic and material space that became the district's brand. Memory, which is modelled there daily, forms an intimate link with space in that collective identity [18]. The idea of continuity arises within that intrinsic relationship, and subjectively constructs the feeling of the permanence of something and/or someone, with respect to a territorial place such as a neighbourhood. In relation to memory as a social construct, Maurice Halbwachs argues that there is no collective memory that does not unfold within a spatial framework [19]. Hence, subjective memory must develop in the realm of everyday life, nurturing the collective identities and social practices of places. Thus, "memory is something constituted and at the same time something constituent; memory is just social praxis" [18].

This current paper is the result of a detailed long-term analysis of Raval's urban transformation process, starting from 2004, which was commissioned by the CCCB and which is continuing as part of the *New urban cultural policy and social transformation* research project funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (National R+D+I Plan, grant reference: RTI2018-096299-B-I00). Our analysis was based on field work carried out from 2002 to 2005 that included 35 interviews, 3 discussion groups, and 6 months of neighbourhood observation. The interviews were conducted with policy makers and public agencies (10), representatives of movements or social organisations (15), and representatives or members of cultural entities (10). From 2012 to 2018, within the framework of the current research project, we updated the data and observations made in our previous work with 6 interviews with cultural agents from the neighbourhood. Our analysis indicated that, in the specific case of urban transformation, authenticity could not be considered the antithesis of falsification, nor was the idea of a popular neighbourhood incompatible with that of a global one. Rather, these elements had combined to form a new memory and district identity by intertwining the reforming elements of the area's medieval past, the myths of the bohemian and popular neighbourhood, and finally, contemporary culture represented by street art.

Urban regeneration and cultural policy

The centrality of culture in urban transformation processes is being increasingly analysed and documented in advanced countries [20,21]. Since the pioneering studies of the 1980s in the U.S. and Britain [22,23], the transformation of central neighbourhoods into a clusters of activity has been analysed in a more positive way as drivers of economic growth and employment-generation [24,25]. Moreover, several authors have noted the growing importance of the creative industries and tourism in the urban economy and their relevance in the generation of urban brands [26-28]. In this context, cultural clusters are becoming important factors of attraction which differentiate consumer products and tourist destinations [15]. Because of this trend, creative industries and tourism businesses are generating more pressure on these city neighbourhoods to adapt to their needs [29]. However, the processes of ‘urban re-functionalisation’ which serve creative industries are also generating resistance from the local inhabitants of these neighbourhoods. A new type of inhabitant, the creative neo-bohemia, are among those involved in the political mobilisation against gentrification. These individuals are attracted by the cultural dynamism of these cultural clusters and the standardisation processes designed by economic and political elites [30-32].

In the context of these transformations the level of local participation acquires a renewed prominence and local governments assume new roles in which they actively promote local development, which often takes shape as the creation of artistic neighbourhoods or clusters of cultural industries [33,34]. Cultural strategies for catalysing urban development include the generation of major events [35], construction of flagship museums [36], and nominations for the European City of Culture [37,38]. Thus, from the 1980s, cultural policy was conceived as an engine of the economy of cities and as a means to leverage the regeneration of urban centres [39]. In this sense, among other policies, local public administrations will seek to emphasise the preservation of the urban fabric by protecting its historical architecture and heritage. These actions aim to develop new spaces for social coexistence such as cultural or leisure infrastructures to attract the educated middle-class to formerly industrial, peripheral, or marginal

spaces which they did not previously visit [14,40]. However, many of these new urban formats—some of which were created by repurposing or appropriating neighbourhood public spaces—are antagonistic to the daily lives of the area's residents, who feel ostracised by them because they seem irrelevant to their own urban space [41].

There is increasing awareness of the benefits generated by urban regeneration policies in terms of the revitalisation of the commercial fabric of areas, and especially, by the creation of cultural concentration clusters [42,43]; this importance is derived not only from infrastructural factors [33], but also from the formal and informal social relationships that shape creative scenes [44,45]. This increased awareness has been transformed into incentive policies for creative cities and industries and has generated several types of artistic cluster, including cultural scenes, industries, and consumption districts [46].

However, the elitising impact in the urban sphere (at the social and gentrifying levels) has also been increasingly noted, thus contributing to the growing economic and social instrumentalisation of culture and its producers as a phenomenon linked to neoliberal capitalism. In other words, the role of culture in urban 'branding' regeneration strategies—which also benefit the real-estate market (Balibrea, 2004; Bianchini, 1993; Borja, 2010; Zukin, 1989; Insulza 2012a-2012b)—and the elaboration of a sprawling discourse about the capacity of culture to face social order problems (Belfiore, 2002). Likewise, in some cases, the policy of large events has generated top-down cultural governance oriented towards tourism and economic impact, sometimes leading to the generation of white elephants (oversized cultural infrastructures) that do not provide adequate social returns to the local citizenship [47,48].

Perhaps this problem can be best summarised in the tension caused by the weakening of policies designed to improve the well-being of the people living in cities (Jordán and Carbonetti, 2007), and in tandem, the strengthening of policies aimed at positioning cities within a highly competitive global market (Mendes, 2007). Starting in the late 1980s, clear regression of the mechanisms of state redistribution and advancement of the market logic as the main forces

responsible for shaping the social life and government of cities (Harvey, 1989), represented a stark break with the norm in the European context. This entrepreneurial focus was expressed at the political level in terms of governance mechanisms, greater participation of the private business sector, and the limited participation of citizens [49]. Thus, some authors have highlighted the importance of a critical and vocal citizenship for the development of more democratic and empowering governance [50].

In this new context of struggle between the market, citizens, and state bureaucracy, the empowering effects of citizen participation in urban redefinition processes and the importance of forging alliances between both the old and new inhabitants of an area, as well as between new and traditional social movements (neighbourhood associations and unions) and have been highlighted [51]. These alliances are important in the development and control of new innovative governance frameworks [52]. However, they must generate a new common imaginary and a neighbourhood brand which differs from the neoliberal banalisation that combines traditional identity with the new uses and creations of the post-Fordist economy [15,53].

In the North American case, gentrification processes combined two parallel and interrelated, but nevertheless, analytically distinct processes: the increase in real estate market prices and re-functionalisation of urban spaces to meet the new needs of post-Fordist capitalism [54,55]. In another process, the local population is being expelled and replaced by global elites or by the so-called creative class [56,57]. However, in the European case, the latter is limited by the lower dynamism and snobbery of the real estate market and by the regulatory action of the welfare state which is usually more protective of individuals living in areas subject to regeneration processes [12,58]. Thus, the combination of these two elements led to the disappearance of local urban memory and creation of a new identity for these spaces in which artists were often considered the 'first-gentrification avant-garde' [59,60]. However, creators have become aware of this process, its impoverishing symbolic-level effect, and the risks of a homogenisation process that could also eventually also expel them [61,62]. Likewise, because of their capacity

for symbolic manipulation, creators have also developed a willingness to reclaim elements of memory and local identity and convert them into artistic products [63]. Moreover, these creations are compatible with the demands of the original inhabitants—against the importation of outside elements such as commercial chains or global fashions, and the promotion of local products and commerce—even as part of urban gentrification processes.

Therefore, creators can play a role in the formation of an alternative urban subculture which promotes these dominant values [64] and in forging new anti-gentrification coalitions and alternative projects for generating neighbourhood identity and cultural revaluation. Likewise, they have symbolic and cultural capital that allows them to generate alternative urban plans and spaces of ‘hope’ for the most disadvantaged inhabitants of the central, grass-roots neighbourhoods most affected by neoliberal urban re-functionalisation processes who are threatened with urban expulsion and social exclusion [65]. From this perspective, allowing these new cultural districts to become sustainable neighbourhoods can open up more participatory and inclusive horizons for urban regeneration [7,66].

Place-making, urban regeneration, and urban memory in the centre of Barcelona

Creativity—comprising material, visual, and discursive symbolic institutional systems that form the image of the city [67]—is becoming a more common component of the new value added to city dynamics. Therefore, for many cities, the opportunity to host powerful events (e.g., social, cultural, or sports activities) is a starting point in redefining itself with a creative ‘city-brand’ [27]. Within this strategic positioning, these types of large-scale projects are instrumentalised to circumscribe an urban policy aiming to build a city image with some element that differentiates it based on its specific qualities and attractions [68]. For example, among other focuses, Barcelona presents itself to the world as a ‘city of culture’ [69] and its regeneration priorities included plans to recover infrastructure and stories bound to its heritage, cultural diversity, and architecture, among other elements. However, it also sponsored internationally recognised

sports (such as Barcelona football club), tourism, and leisure (beaches, gastronomy, etc.) to help cement its image and branding.

The more recent construction of new cultural infrastructures (e.g., the Fílmoteca, CCCB, and Museum of Contemporary Art of Barcelona [MACBA], among many others) has also contributed to the growth of its cultural capital [70]. Moreover, the regeneration and conversion of urban spaces into centres for creation and innovation (e.g., with 22@ in Poblenou, and creation factories such as La Escocesa and Hangar) and hosting global events such as the World Forum of Cultures in 2004, have consolidated this image as a cultural city [71]. Also, the local government developed significant public arts planning in the city after its Olympic nomination in 1986. The many important works installed in Barcelona during those years include *Pez* (1992) by Frank Gehry; *Cat* by Fernando Botero (bought by Barcelona City Council in 1987 and finally placed on the Rambla del Raval in 2003); *The head of Barcelona* (1991–1992) by Roy Lichtenstein and made by Diego Delgado Rajado; the facility *Cambio (Utsurohi)* by Aiko Miyawaki (1990); *The Wounded Star* (1992) by Rebecca Horn; and *Cerillas* (1992) by Claes Oldenburg, among many others.

Some authors have highlighted the negative or gentrifying consequences of this transformation in local communities [72-74]. These authors usually view culture from a ‘conspiratorial’ perspective, as an instrumentalising and passive element of gentrifying strategies [75]. However, as we discuss below, this process is more complex. First, from the 1980s, the Raval became a neighbourhood with a high percentage of immigrants, and a part of its population remained there thanks to social housing policies [12,76]. Second, cultural sectors, especially emerging and alternative ones, played an active role in giving value to the neighbourhood, thus favouring its conservation and encouraging neighbourhood participation [12]¹.

Urban regeneration and the construction of a new memory: the new Raval and the memory of the *barrio chino*

One of the largest and most ambitious projects was the transformation of the city centre in general, and the Raval in particular. In the second half of the 20th century, this neighbourhood had undergone an intense process of urban degradation as the result of a combination of social, urban, and cultural policies [77,78]. Within this framework, the idea to develop the cultural district of northern Raval, promoted by successive public administrations since the 1980s, crystallised when a reuse project for the former Casa de la Caridad hospice for cultural purposes was proposed. In the mid-1990s, this building eventually became the CCCB and MACBA, flagships whose inauguration marked the ‘before and after’ of the neighbourhood and the regeneration process [17,79]. Today, this cultural district is an epicentre of cultural institutions and numerous cultural and creative sector companies and professionals, including theatres, design studios, art galleries, and publishers [80].

Thus, this formerly degraded and stigmatised neighbourhood has undergone great social change and now hosts new activities and cultural and educational uses, although it does still suffer from serious problems related to social exclusion [81]. The urban metamorphosis of the physical environment of this area was accompanied by population changes, starting at the beginning of the 20th century but especially so in the last two decades—sustained by migration from countries such as Ecuador, the Philippines, Morocco, Bangladesh, and Pakistan; of the 48.2 thousand inhabitants of Raval in 2019, 29.1 thousand (60.3%) had been born abroad, compared to an average of 26.2% for the whole of Barcelona [82].

Since the early 20th century, the centre of Barcelona was one of the southern European territories best known as a *barrio chino* red-light district because of its mentions in Catalan, Spanish, and international literature [83]. In addition, the territory we now consider the Raval, did not originally exist as an administrative unit, rather, it was divided into District VI in the north and District V in the south. However, at the popular level this urban space was known as Chinatown as the result of a journalistic and literary invention that combined two types of looks. On the one hand, *barrio chino* evoked the bohemian, ‘canaille’ atmosphere of a café-concert neighbourhood with international cabarets. This image corresponded to a populist, nostalgic,

positive, and romantic perspective [84]. On the other hand, was the *barrio chino* constructed by the sensationalist press and novelists as representative of the dark side of popular life—as a red-light district associated with crime, deviant sex, and drug abuse [77].

As we will see below, from the beginning of the reforms in the 1980s, there was a consensus that the process of urban regeneration changed the symbolic status of the neighbourhood from its largely stigmatised *barrio chino* designation. At the same time, a new name was being created for the area (which was recovered from forgotten medieval origins) to try to link the splendour of the city's medieval era with its urban heritage. Therefore, Raval's name is the product of a contemporary invention:

(...) by 1964, nobody knew what the Raval neighbourhood was. I wrote a paper for the newspaper, *Escenas del Barrio Chino*, and I was with people who have lived here a lifetime, and none of those present did not remember that, as a young man, the Raval was called by (...) another name, district V. It is the only neighbourhood in Barcelona that has been known by the name of a district, the only one, there has been no other [85]. (authors' note: translated from Catalan).

The fact that it was the only area in Barcelona that was called by its administrative designation and that did not have an official neighbourhood name indicates, on the one hand, the inherent desire to escape the stigma of the 'bad name' of *barrio chino* and, on the other, the problem of the absence of a common urban and citizen identity:

The Distrito Quinto is a name that became popular; There is even a Julio Coll movie called this, and it is based on a novel by Josep Maria Espinàs. This nomenclature was so entrenched that even when the neighbourhood association was created, in 1974, it was named the Fifth District Neighbourhood Association. It would not be until 1984 that the districts of Barcelona changed, and the Fifth District became the First. It is then that the name of Raval reappeared and took root strongly [85].

The name of the old neighbourhood was confusing and fragmented because, at the time, the territory now referred to as Raval was not a neighbourhood in the sense that we traditionally

understand it as a common living space. In reality, this quarter of the city was, and partly continues to be, a set of well-differentiated urban territories, whose only common element was its location between the second and third walls of the medieval city and the fact that it had been urbanised in the 19th century. That is why the Barcelonan playwright and son of the neighbourhood, writer Benet i Jornet, stated:

The Raval does not know what it is. There was never, never was anything called the Raval! It's an invention! There were several neighbourhoods: the *Chino*, with a world full of misery and colour at the same time, that of Carmen, where I lived, that of Padró Square, and others. It was a network of neighbourhoods. El Raval was the street that was immediately outside the walls, and was invented to forget the *Chino* [86].

However, the reform of the neighbourhood in the 1980s and 1990s did not eliminate its recent memory, but instead, revived the history and urban legend of this early 20th century district. Nonetheless, there is insistent theorisation that the name Raval was imposed top-down by the state to eliminate the *barrio chino* connotation [9]. In this sense, the name changes during the process and its adoption by the neighbourhood's social agents (including community social movements) was not neutral and was a commitment to reform as a process of symbolic change. Thus, Raval would be the 'toponymy' of the place-making project started in the 1980s and we cannot consider it as a distortion of the memory imposed by the public administration. From the 1970s, this nomenclature was also used by the neighbourhood movement, because it allowed them to designate the entire territory and allow the community associations to present themselves in a more positive way as a single and more powerful interlocutor [87].

Therefore, the process of place-making in this neighbourhood was based on the recovery and resignification the formerly socially stigmatised *barrio chino* space, as well as the replacement of the name used to refer to it. In contrast, during the 1990s and 2000s, the use of the word *chino* by the radical left (such as anti-globalisation or the *indignados* social movements) in alliance with visual artists became, to some extent, a critical claim towards these urban reform processes, which they interpreted as a gentrification project [9,88]. This can be seen in the

graffiti on the streets of Raval that contrasted the two names as “True *Chino*, Plastic Raval”, thus reclaiming the memory of the *chino* red-light district with paintings and stickers protesting against the new hipster inhabitants of the area and the effects of cultural institutions and urban real-estate speculation.

Figure 1 – Paintings and stickers protesting against gentrification in Raval.

Hence, in the case of Raval, the historical memory and names of the spaces were not imposed only from a place of power. Rather, their use extended through the local population because they referred to a new reality of transformation and expressed a will or desire for change. This change also increased in its breadth and complexity with the installation of cultural institutions such as the CCCB and, starting from the foundational idea of reform in Raval (the *Plan Del Liceu al Seminari*), and by recovering historic buildings such as the Hospital de la Santa Creu or Casa de la Caridad to convert them into spaces of cultural revitalisation which would honour the memory of the neighbourhood [89].

From urban regeneration to cultural revitalisation: cultural institutions and the place-making of Raval

This cluster of cultural institutions in Raval was developed in the context of very complex and ambitious urban regeneration plans that attempted to achieve urban change without causing destruction [90]. As we have already mentioned, this process generated long-standing controversy about the social effects of these policies, and built the image of a citizenship that scrutinises the city’s urban and cultural policies [15,78]. Thus, the first outline of the content and orientation of Raval emerged with the development of the first democratic cultural policy led by socialist city councils under the leadership of Mayor Pascual Maragall [91]. Josep

Subirós, the former Cultural Commissioner for the city, highlighted the broad involvement of Mayor Maragall and his vision of the cultural importance of urban transformation as follows:

With Mayor Maragall, I believe that there is a closer sensitivity in the first place to cultural issues, perhaps due to family tradition, personal character, and a very strong link between all municipal policies, and especially cultural policies, and a certain idea of urban restructuring. Much more clearly, [given] that it did not exist before. (...) [92].

Maragall's vision of culture was based on a project that would transform the city into a global metropolis with a strong Mediterranean character (McNeill 2001). Similarly, the Museum Plan, which had been prepared during the mandate of the Councillor for Culture, Maria Aurèlia Capmany—a renowned writer and cultural manager—was presented in 1985 [93]. This plan proposed reordering and planning the rich but untidy and neglected museum map of the city of Barcelona by creating groups of museums located in five main areas: Montjuïc, Raval, Gotic, La Ribera, and Ciutadella. The criteria used to form these groups considered the value of the buildings, visitor types, collections, and their relationship with other facilities, as well as the 'urban facts' and possibilities for synthesis so that these museums would evoke a "history of the city and a project for the future" [93] Specifically regarding the Raval area, the plan stated the following:

(...) The Raval also has two characteristics: on the one hand, the dense layout within the streets and blocks, without any way that dares to cut the old medieval division. Therefore, future museums must be consistent with this characteristic aspect and [should] be broken up into appropriate units with their access channels. On the other hand, the existence of institutions closely linked to research and individual activities (especially libraries) drives as a counterpoint to think about the possibility of proposing certain museum activities related to the idea of 'modernity' or at least [ones] practiced mostly by young people, which, together with the proximity of the most popular and cosmopolitan area, La Rambla, would also be consistent with this approach [93].

Consequently, since its inception, the cultural planning of the neighbourhood sought to combine the heritage dimension—and the specific characteristics of the old neighbourhood—with a new irruption of contemporary culture in its facilities. Thus, the initial concept of the aggregation of cultural institutions would go on to become a cultural ‘oil stain’ which would progressively impregnate the remaining urban network, regenerating it via their beneficial influence. In addition, as we have already mentioned, the 1986 nomination of Barcelona for the 1992 Olympic Games was the starting point for the redevelopment of old infrastructure and cultural projects. One year after the nomination (in July 1987), the idea of developing a new, large-scale cultural infrastructure for the neighbourhood was presented and hence, the project to create the MACBA was born. In the press conference organised to present the project, Richard Meier (the architect that mayor Maragall had personally convinced to design the MACBA) stated that:

[The MACBA] is a very important centre for the city. Maybe it represents for Barcelona a transformation similar to the one that the Pompidou Centre represented for the Marais neighbourhood in Paris (...). But the possibility of renovating such a unique neighbourhood from a building is very attractive to me. We’ll see what happens. Now is the time to sow [94].

Nevertheless, Richard Meier was not alone in conceiving culture as a tool for neighbourhood regeneration, nor was he solely responsible for implementing these ideas. Thus, this idea was also shared and promoted by Josep Subirós, who compared the process he envisioned for Raval with other examples of urban regeneration implemented in Europe and the U.S. during the 1980s, while also introducing an important nuance:

One of the formulas [used] successfully to deal with this phenomenon [urban degradation]—in the Marais of Paris, in the Old Port of Marseille, in the City of London, in the port areas of San Francisco or Boston, etc.—is precisely, the implementation of new types of activities in these areas, and especially, commercial and cultural services [as] exponents of cultural creativity [92].

Accordingly, Subirós did not want a process of change led by the market and its mercantile or banalising effects on urban land, but rather, anticipated criticism about the possible

depersonalisation and gentrification effects. Hence, he ensured that the process would be driven by public cultural facilities to try to avoid these problems. Therefore, the great cultural facilities project that opened its doors in the mid-1990s (the CCCB in 1994 and MACBA in 1995) was fully aware both that it represented the flagship of the neighbourhood transformation and of the risks associated with that responsibility. Some people responsible for these institutions took an unkind view of their expected role in the social change of the neighbourhood:

At that time, the Raval was an impoverished neighbourhood (...). So, I think that a new life has come to the Raval, more, a cultural life that is gradually escaping little [by little], and I think it will be very important when the university arrives and, [there will be] a new life under immigration. And I think this has given rise to an unstable but interesting situation [92].

Therefore, the 1994 opening of the CCCB in the renewed Casa de la Caridad building kick-started the process of place-making. The CCCB has since become the clowning jewel of the neighbourhood regeneration cultural project, especially given that from its inception, its development considered the urban complexity and identity of Raval. Thus, the CCCB became a cultural lightning rod and hosted a series of successful exhibitions related to cities, writers, and the urban environment. This orientation also had the unforeseen effect of promoting the area as a centre for city-based artists and artistic projects, which gave rise to urban culture festivals such as Sónar [95]. However, one of the CCCB's most significant influential moments came in the late 1990s with a large interactive and participative cultural installation with associated activities, called *Escenas del Raval* ('Scenes of Raval'). This exhibition, conceived as an active and open creation, collected dialogues from neighbourhood residents which were sometimes casual but other times were more formalised as interviews, colloquiums, or discussion groups, etc. Other social and cultural entities, including the Philippine Community of Barcelona, lbn Batuta sociocultural association, Association of Neighbours of the Raval of Ciutat Vella, and Raval Neighbourhood Choral Coordinator also participated. The 1998–1999 CCCB report confirmed the intention of this last exhibition thus:

In its configuration as a popular neighbourhood, the Raval is an engine of life in full transformation. A fabric in which relationships, creations, and lives are stamped. A neighbourhood where various spaces converge, for memory, for pleasure, for commerce (...) Claudio Zulián devised the *Escenes del Raval* project, which reflected the diversity of this central core of Barcelona. The show made a tour of the known neighbourhood but also [of] the unknown: seven scenes spread across different spaces of the CCCB [that] reflected it. Scenes of architecture or memories, of foreigners or pleasures. Seven spaces designed through plans, representative buildings, sounds, images, texts, and computers to bring together information [96].

Accordingly, the link between the neighbourhood artists and residents was enhanced with the CCCB project, *The City of Words*, which made artistic and literary work the protagonists and brought museums and libraries out into everyday life for a few days with the aim of exchanging attitudes and knowledge. The 2000 edition, under the slogan ‘The path of memory’, tried to open up—or retrieve—the memories of residents of the area via words that were hung beautifully on the facades of their buildings.

In the 1990s, another urban regeneration project was planned in the Raval with the construction of the Filmoteca de Catalunya in the heart of the neighbourhood, thereby creating a public square in a district which had insufficient public space. In this case, it was used to reinforce historical memory by naming the square after the historical anarchist leader, Salvador Seguí, who was assassinated in a neighbouring street in 1923. This naming policy, which non-systematically recovered historical memory was applied in various spaces, with dedications to local writers and politicians as the Plaça Pieyre André de Mandiargues, Carrer Manuel Vázquez Montalban, Plaça de Jean Genet, or the Biblioteca Andreu Nin, all of which recalled the historical memory of Raval before of the Spanish Civil War and subsequent era of Francoist repression. Moreover, during the 2000s, the local government developed campaigns to highlight the culturally vibrant character of the neighbourhood in order to associate culture and creativity with the Raval brand.

Figure 2 – The ‘Come to the Raval of imagination’ campaign by Raval Cultural (2015).

Finally, the public events hosted in Raval and organised by the community to help recover its unique local history through symbolic content showing the memory of the neighbourhood, included the *Ravalejar* project, which tried to define the neighbourhood, its personality, and the feelings shared by its inhabitants.

Figure 3 – The *Ravalejar* branding project (2013).

Conclusions

The development of major cultural and sporting events in Barcelona made it possible to build a city brand related to the creative and tourist industries that appeals to international market circuits [69,70]. However, beyond generating strategies based on their cultural component, cities also take advantage of this competitive framework as a way to make places with their own unique images. Thus, respect for singularities and some degree of citizen participation (through councils and strategic planning) in urban regeneration and cultural planning processes has become an essential axis in place-making [97,98]. However, a positive balance must be struck with the phenomena of gentrification and by limiting citizen participation in the processes of urban regeneration to some extent. This explains the claims of—and growing resistance to—bottom-up urban governance made both by the original inhabitants as well as the neo-bohemia living in these areas [49,99,100].

The case in Barcelona analysed in this work exemplifies the sense in which the singularity of the Raval neighbourhood was not only maintained, but also recognised and promoted as a factor

that differentiates this urban space. A new name was invented for this neighbourhood to try to redefine its previous stigma at least partially and to open the neighbourhood up, to some extent, to the rest of the city. This simultaneous bi-directional cultural renewal, socio-urban development, and promotion of cultural memory was seen in CCCB projects, and more generally, in different projects implemented locally in Raval by its own residents. Likewise, Raval's desire for regeneration, as elaborated in the local government town plans, was implemented during the 1980s and 1990s, before concerns about participation in place-making [14,101], social inclusion, and respect for the area's cultural legacy and the memory of its inhabitants were fully made known and considered.

Finally, despite many forecasts about the gentrification of the neighbourhood and its conversion into a theme park, Raval continues to be a vibrant, diverse, and sometimes still problematic area at the urban level—the latter being related to the fact that even now it is stigmatised by phenomena such as drug trafficking and small-scale robberies [12,102]. In this sense, the place-making in the centre of Barcelona has generated a paradoxical situation in which, on the one hand, the neighbourhood constitutes a cultural and leisure cluster, while on the other, it is a multicultural and socially diverse place with a street-level ambiance derived from immigration and a neo-bohemian vibe. To conclude, despite its social complexities, the place-making of Raval has mostly been successful. The district has been able to symbolically connect to its medieval past, re-evaluate its more bohemian side and *barrio chino* red-light district memory, and develop its brand as a vibrant and creative place.

Notes

¹ The process of creating the memory and identity of Raval is embedded in the urban regeneration processes promoted since the time of the election of a democratic local government in the 1980s and was part of the so-called Barcelona model [69,90], which some authors have described as a process of gentrification. However, the main goal of this article was not to determine whether a gentrification process exists in Raval because this is already the subject of several articles such as those by Sargatal

[103,104], Tabakman [105], Riol Carvajal [106], Delgado [73], Mónica Degen [8,72] or Malcom Miles [74,107], and Fernández Gonzalez [9], among others. These studies examined some features of the urban and social transformation of the Raval district, and all take a denunciatory stance against the local urban policy and its perverse effects on local communities. They also expose some real-estate speculation processes, the elitising course of some urban spaces, or the mercantilist drift of urban planning processes from the 2000s [9]. Other authors have examined the process from a global perspective, comparing the community's situation before and after the reforms and admit that, despite the negative effects mentioned above, it can be generally argued that the local community was not expelled [78] and that the residents affected by the reforms were rehoused in newly constructed homes within the district, resulting in a significant improvement in their living conditions [76] as well as the revitalisation of their public spaces which are now intensively used by a multiplicity of social groups [102]. The reform of Raval has some grey areas and dark sides such as the growing uses of the urban space for tourism [108] but for the most part, the social and cultural continuity of the district has not been cut short. However, it must now cope with a social and urban environment which is more open to influxes from the rest of the city and the country (Aisa and Vidal, 2005). Thus, 20 years after the start of the reforms—and with a broader longitudinal perspective than the articles cited above—we were able to verify that Raval is the most socially and culturally diverse district in Barcelona, with almost 50% of its residents having been born or living there before the reforms and with 15% being new, mostly young and middle-class residents, either from Spain or other EU countries, whose work is usually related to the creative professions [12,109].

References

1. Moulin, R. *L'Artiste, l'institution et le marché*, Flammarion: Paris, 1997; pp. 437.
2. Evans, G. *Cultural Planning: An urban renaissance?* Routledge: Londres, 2001;.
3. Sibalis, M. Urban Space and Homosexuality: The Example of the Marais, Paris' 'Gay Ghetto'. *Urban Studies* **2004**, *41*, 1739-1758.
4. Peterson, K. The distribution and dynamics of uncertainty in art galleries: A case study of new dealership in the Parisian art market, 1985-1990. *Poetics* **1997**, *25*, 241-263.
5. Ross, K. Paris assassinat. In *Els límits del museu* Fundació Tàpies: Barcelona, 1995; pp. 40-67.
6. Moomas, H. Cultural clusters and the post-industrial city: towards a remapping of urban cultural policy. *Urban Studies* **2004**, *41*, 507-532.
7. Kagan, S.; Hahn, J. Creative cities and (Un)Sustainability: From Creative Class to Sustainable Creative Cities. *Culture and Local Governance* **2011**, *3*: 1-2, 11-27.
8. Degen, M. Fighting for the global catwalk: formalizing public life in Castlefield (Manchester) and diluting public life in el Raval (Barcelona). *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* **2003**, *27*, 867-880.
9. Fernández González, M. *Matar el Chino. Entre la revolución urbanística y el asedio urbano en el barrio del Raval de Barcelona*, Virus Editorial: Barcelona, 2014;.
10. Delgado, M. *La ciudad mentirosa: fraude y miseria del "modelo Barcelona"*, Los Libros de la Catarata: Madrid, 2007;.
11. Anonymized.
12. Anonymized.
13. Bonin-Rodriguez, P. *Performing Policy. How Contemporary Politics and Cultural Programs Redefined U.S. Artists for the Twenty-First Century*, Palgrave: New York, 2015;.
14. Redaelli, E. *Connecting Arts and Place. Cultural Policy and American Cities*, Palgrave: New York, 2019;.
15. Anonymized
16. Casellas, A.; Dot Jutgla, E.; Pallares-Barbera, M. Creación de imagen, visibilidad y turismo como estrategias de crecimiento económico de la ciudad. *Finisterra* **2010**, *XLV*, 153-172.

17. Casellas, A. Barcelona's Urban Landscape: The Historical Making of a Tourist Product. *Journal of Urban History* **2009**, *35*, 815-832.
18. Pineda, K.; Edith, E. Habitando el barrio La Fama: espacios de identidad colectiva y memoria, *34*, 161-182. Doi: [dx.doi.org/10.12804/territ34.2016.07](https://doi.org/10.12804/territ34.2016.07). *Territorios* **2016**, *36*, 161-182.
19. Halbwachs, M. *Les cadres sociaux de la mémoire*, Albin Michel: Paris, 2001; pp. 367.
20. García, B. Cultural Policy and Urban Regeneration in Western European Cities: Lessons from Experience, Prospects for the Future. *Local Economy* **2004**, *19*, 312-326.
21. Montgomery, J. Cultural Quarters as Mechanisms for Urban Regeneration. Part 1: Conceptualising Cultural Quarters. *Planning Practice and Research* **2003**, *18*, 293-293.
22. Bianchini, F.; Parkinson, M. *Cultural Policy and Urban Regeneration: The West European Experience*, Manchester University Press; Manchester, 1993; pp. 1.
23. Zukin, S. *The cultures of cities*, Blackwell: Oxford, 1995;.
24. Markusen, A.; Schrock, G. The Artistic Dividend: Urban Artistic Specialisation and Economic Development Implications. *Urban Studies* **2006**, *43*, 1661-1686.
25. Williams, S.; Currid-Halkett, E. The emergence of Los Angeles as a fashion hub: A comparative spatial analysis of the New York and Los Angeles fashion industries. *Urban Stud* **2011**, *48*, 3043-3066, DOI 10.1177/0042098010392080. (accessed on 5 December 2012).
26. Pike, A. *Brands and branding geographies*, Edward Elgar: Cheltenham; Northampton, 2011; pp. 356.
27. Evans, G. Hard-Branding the cultural city-from Prado to Prada. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* **2003**, *27*, 417-440 (accessed on 5 December 2012).
28. Vanolo, A. The image of the creative city: Some reflections on urban branding in Turin. *Cities* **2008**, *25*, 370-382.
29. Degen, M.; García, M. The Transformation of the Barcelona Model?: An Analysis of Culture, Urban Regeneration and Governance. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* **2012**, *36*, 1022-1038.
30. Julier, G. Urban Designscapes and the Production of Aesthetic Consent. *Urban Studies* **2005**, *42*, 869-887.

31. Julier, G. Design activism meets place-branding: reconfiguring urban representation and everyday practice. In *Brand and Branding Geographies*; Pike, A., Ed.; Edward Elgar: Cheltenham; Northampton, 2011; pp. 221-238.
32. Anonymized
33. Scott, A. *The Cultural Economy of Cities*, Sage in association with Theory, Culture & Society. Nottingham Trent University: London [etc.], 2000;.
34. Scott, A. Cultural economy and the creative field of the city. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography* **2010**, *92*, 115-130.
35. García, B. Urban regeneration, arts programming and major events: Glasgow 1990, Sydney 2000 and Barcelona 2004 . *International Journal of Cultural Policy* **2004**, *10*, 103-118.
36. Bianchini, F. *Urban Cultural Policy in Britain and Europe: Towards Cultural Planning*, Institute for Cultural Policy Studies: London, 1993;.
37. Mooney, G. Cultural Policy as Urban Transformation? Critical Reflections on Glasgow, European City of Culture 1990. *Local Economy* **2004**, *19*, 327-340.
38. Balsas, C.J.L. City Centre Regeneration in the Context of the 2001 European Capital of Culture in Porto, Portugal. *Local Economy* **2004**, *19*, 396-410.
39. Landry, C.; Bianchini, F. *The creative city*, Demos: London, 1995;.
40. Stevenson, D.; Magee, L. Art and space: Creative infrastructure and cultural capital in Sydney, Australia. *Journal of Sociology* **2017**, *53*, 839-861.
41. Degen, M. Timescapes of urban change: The temporalities of regenerated streets. *Sociol Rev* **2018**, *Onlinefirst*, 1-27.
42. Markusen, A. Sticky Places in Slippery Space: A Typology of Industrial Districts. *Economic Geography* **1996**, *72*, 293-313.
43. Markusen, A.; Gadwa, A. Arts and Culture in Urban or Regional Planning: A Review and Research Agenda. *Journal of Planning Education and Research* **2010**, *29*, 379-391.
44. Currid, E. *The Warhol economy: how fashion, art, and music drive New York City*, Princeton University Press: 2007;.
45. Currid, E.; Williams, S. The geography of buzz: art, culture and the social milieu in Los Angeles and New York. *Journal of Economic Geography* **2010**, *10*, 423-451.
46. Anonymized
47. Anonymized

48. Afeltowicz, Ł.; Olechnicki, K.; Szlendak, T.; Wróblewski, M.; Gądecki, J. How to make the white elephant work: findings from ethnographic research into Polish new cultural institutions. *International Journal of Cultural Policy* **2020**, 1-17.
49. Blakeley, G. Local Governance and Local Democracy: The Barcelona Model. *Local Government Studies* **2005**, *31*, 149-165, DOI 10.1080/03003930500031959. Available online: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03003930500031959>.
50. Geissel, B. Do Critical Citizens Foster Better Governance? A Comparative Study. *West European Politics* **2008**, *31*, 855-873.
51. Parés, M.; Bonet-Martí, J.; Martí-Costa, M. Does Participation Really Matter in Urban Regeneration Policies? Exploring Governance Networks in Catalonia (Spain). *Urban Affairs Review* **2012**, *48*, 238-271, DOI 10.1177/1078087411423352.
52. Swyngedouw, E. Governance Innovation and the Citizen: The Janus Face of Governance-beyond-the-State. *Urban Studies* **2005**, *42*, 1991-2006.
53. Lloyd, R. *Neo-Bohemia: Art and commerce in the postindustrial city*, Routledge: Nueva York, 2010;.
54. Zukin, S. *The culture of cities*, Blackwell: Oxford, 1995;.
55. Smith, N. *The New Urban Frontier: Gentrification and the Revanchist City*, Routledge: New York, 1996;.
56. Markusen, A. Urban development and the politics of a creative class: evidence from a study of artists. *Environment and Planning A* **2006**, *38*, 1921 – 1940-1921 – 1940.
57. Kostelanetz, R. *Soho: The Rise and Fall of an Artist's Colony*, Routledge: Nueva York, 2003;.
58. Wacquant, L. Pour en finir avec le mythe des ‘cités-ghettos’: les différences entre la France et les Etats-Unis. *Annales de la recherche urbaine* **1992**, *54*, 20-30.
59. Lloyd, R. Neo-Bohemia: Art and Neighborhood Redevelopment in Chicago. *Journal of Urban Affairs* **2002**, *24*, 517-532.
60. Deutsche, R.; Gendel Ryan, C. The Fine Art of Gentrification. *October* **1984**, *31*, 91-111.
61. Zukin, S. *Loft Living: Culture and Capital in Urban Change*, The Johns Hopkins University Press: Baltimore, 1982;.
62. Zukin, S.; Braslow, L. The life cycle of New York’s creative districts: Reflections on the unanticipated consequences of unplanned cultural zones. *City, Culture and Society* **2011**, *2*, 131-140, DOI 10.1016/j.ccs.2011.06.003.

63. Chalvon-Demersay, S. *Le triangle du XIVE: Des nouveaux habitants dans un vieux quartier de Paris*, Paris: Métailée, 1999;.
64. Fischer, C.S. The Subcultural Theory of Urbanism: A Twentieth-Year Assessment. *American Journal of Sociology* **1995**, *101*, 543-577.
65. Novy, J.; Colomb, C. Struggling for the Right to the (Creative) City in Berlin and Hamburg: New Urban Social Movements, New ?Spaces of Hope?? *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* **2013**, *37*, 1816-1838.
66. Kirchberg, V.; Kagan, S. The roles of artists in the emergence of creative sustainable cities: Theoretical clues and empirical illustrations. *City, Culture and Society* **2013**, *4*, 137-152, DOI <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccs.2013.04.001>.
67. Jones, C.; Svejenova, S. The architecture of city identities: A multimodal study of Barcelona and Boston. *Research in the Sociology of Organizations* **2017**, *54B*, 42.
68. Julier, G. Urban Designscapes and the Production of Aesthetic Content. *Urban Studies* **2005**, *42*, 869-887.
69. González, S. Bilbao and Barcelona 'in Motion'. How Urban Regeneration 'Models' Travel and Mutate in the Global Flows of Policy Tourism. *Urban Studies* **2011**, *48*, 1397-1418, DOI 10.1177/0042098010374510.
70. Anonymized
71. Anonymized
72. Degen, M. *Sensing cities :regenerating public life in Barcelona and Manchester*, Routledge: London, 2008; pp. 225.
73. Delgado, M. La artistización de las políticas urbanas. El lugar de la cultura en las dinámicas de reapropiación capitalista de la ciudad. *Scripta Nova: revista electrónica de geografía y ciencias sociales* **2008**, *12*, 1-26 Available online: <http://www.raco.cat/index.php/ScriptaNova/article/view/115467>.
74. Miles, M. Drawn and quartered: El Raval and the Haussmannization of Barcelona. In *City of Quarters: Urban Villages in the Contemporary City*; Jayne, M.; Jayne, M., Eds.; Ashgate: Aldershot, 2004; pp. 37-55.
75. Harvey, D. El arte de la renta: la globalización y la mercantilización de la cultura. In *Capital financiero, propiedad inmobiliaria y cultura*; Harvey, D.; Smith, N., Eds.; Museu d'Art Contemporani de Barcelona: Barcelona, 2005; pp. 29-58.
76. Aramburu, M. *Bajo el signo del gueto. Imágenes del "inmigrante" en Ciutat Vella*. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona: PhD Thesis. Barcelona, 2000;.
77. Aisa, F.; Vidal, M. *El Raval: un espai al marge*, Editorial Base: Barcelona, 2005;.

78. Martínez Rigol, S.
El retorn al centre de la ciutat. La reestructuració del Raval entre la renovació i la gentrificació. , Universitat de Barcelona: PhD thesis. Barcelona, 2000;.
79. Anonymized
80. Anonymized
81. Fundació Tot Raval *Estudi Econòmic i Comercial del Raval 2010-2011*, Fundació Tot Raval: Barcelona, 2012;.
82. Ajuntament de Barcelona *Lectura del Padró Municipal d'Habitants a 1 gener 2019.* , Ajuntament de Barcelona. Departament d'Estadística i Difusió de Dades: Barcelona, 2019;.
83. Casanova, P. *La república mundial de las letras*, Anagrama: Barcelona, 2001;.
84. Villar, P. *Historia y leyenda del Barrio Chino (1900-1992)*, La Campana: Barcelona, 1997;.
85. Huertas Claveria, J.M. Entrevista. In *Escenas del Raval*; Zulian, C., Ed.; CCCB: Barcelona, 1998; pp. 10-22.
86. Benet i Jornet, Josep Maria Entrevista. *Ciutat Vella* **2004**, 55, 3-4.
87. Domingo, M.; Bonet, M.R. *Barcelona i els moviments socials urbans*, Fundació Jaume Bofill – Editorial Mediterrània: Barcelona, 1988;.
88. Delgado, M. Artivismo y pospolítica. Sobre la estetización de las luchas sociales en contextos urbanos . *Quaderns-e. Institut Català d'Antropologia* **2013**, 18, 68-80.
89. Bohigas, O. *Gràcies i desgràcies culturals de Barcelona*, Àrea de Cultura. Ajuntament de Barcelona: Barcelona, 1993;.
90. PROCIVESA *Ciutat Vella Ciutat construïda*, El Cep i la Nansa: Barcelona, 2002;.
91. McNeill, D. Mapping the European Urban Left: The Barcelona Experience. *Antipode* **2003**, 35, 74-94, DOI 10.1111/1467-8330.00303.
92. Subirós, J. *Interview with Josep Subirós, former city cultural commissioner and delegate of the Casa de la Caridad Project, 07-29-2003*, CCCB-UAB: Barcelona, 2003;.
93. Ajuntament de Barcelona *Pla de Museus de Barcelona*, Ajuntament de Barcelona: Barcelona, 1985;.
94. Meier, R. Interview of Richard Meier. *La Vanguardia* **1987**, 29-01-1987.

95. Chalcraft, J.; Magaouda, P. 'Space is the Place'. The global localities of the Sónar and WOMAD music festivals . In *Festivals and the Cultural Public Sphere*; Gerard Delanty, e.a., Ed.; Routledge: London, 2011; Volume Cap. 11, pp. 1-17.
96. CCCB *Memoria del CCCB*, Centro de Cultura Contemporanea de Barcelona: Barcelona, 2000;.
97. Redaelli, E. Creative placemaking and theories of art: Analyzing a place-based NEA policy in Portland, OR. *Cities* **2018**, 72, 403-410, DOI <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2017.10.001> ".
98. Marshall, T. Urban Planning and Governance: Is there a Barcelona Model? *International Planning Studies* **2000**, 5, 299-319, DOI 10.1080/713672855.
99. Martí-Costa, M.; Pradel i Miquel, M. The knowledge city against urban creativity? Artists' workshops and urban regeneration in Barcelona. *European Urban and Regional Studies* **2012**, 19, 92-108.
100. Anonymized
101. Duxbury, N.; Jeannotte, M.S. From the bottom-up: culture in community sustainability planning. *3rd ESA Sociology of Culture research mid-term Conference* **2010**, 1-15.
102. Degen, M. Urban Regeneration and "Resistance of Place": Foregrounding Time and Experience. *Space and Culture* **2017**, 20, 141-155.
103. Sargatal, A. Gentrificación e inmigración en los centros históricos: el caso del Raval de Barcelona. *Scripta Nova. Revista Electrónica de Geografía y Ciencias Sociales* **2001**, 94, <http://www.ub.edu/geocrit/sn-94-66.htm>.
104. Sargatal, A. La vivienda en el centro histórico de Barcelona. El caso de la Rambla del Raval. *Scripta Nova. Revista Electrónica de Geografía y Ciencias Sociales* **2003**, 146, <http://www.ub.edu/geocrit/sn/sn-146%28069%29.htm#14>.
105. Tabakman, E. El Casc Antic de Barcelona: actuación urbanística o "limpieza social"? *Scripta Nova. Revista Electrónica de Geografía y Ciencias Sociales* **2001**, 94, <http://www.ub.edu/geocrit/sn-94-67.htm>.
106. Riol Carvajal, E. La vivienda de los inmigrantes en Barcelona: el caso del colectivo pakistání. *Scripta Nova. Revista Electrónica de Geografía y Ciencias Sociales* **2003**, 146, [http://www.ub.es/geocrit/sn/sn-146\(059\).htm](http://www.ub.es/geocrit/sn/sn-146(059).htm).
107. Miles, M. Interruptions: Testing the Rhetoric of Culturally Led Urban Development. *Urban Studies* **2005**, 42, 889-911, DOI 10.1080/00420980500107375.
108. Hughes, N. 'Tourists go home': anti-tourism industry protest in Barcelona. *Social Movement Studies* **2018**, 17, 471-477.

109. Ajuntament de Barcelona *Raval Cultural. Foment de la Ciutat*, Ajuntament de Barcelona: Barcelona, 2017;.